

MOVING TO COMPOSITE FUSELAGE DESIGN

F.K. Arakaki^{1*}¹ Development Technological, EMBRAER S.A., São José dos Campos, Brazil.* Corresponding author (francisco.arakaki@embraer.com.br)**Keywords:** *composite material, post-buckling, design criteria.***1 Introduction**

Composite structure design has many features such as the conception, the ability of the manufacture, the analysis criteria, the certification and maintenance. The optimum design combines the maximum of this requirements with weight saving. In accordance with the reference [1] cost and weight evaluation of fuselage panel was considered in the design concepts. Matsui and Sato in the reference [2], developed a proof-of-concept business jet that utilizes an all-composite fuselage. Fig. 1, shows the stringers and frame cross-section of this concept. Also, the main feature of this fuselage structure was to reduce both weight and cost. Another key feature mentioned is that a buckling tolerance design was adopted for the skin. That is, the shear buckling was allowed beyond 50% limit load (see Fig 2. - Shear Buckling Test). The material and structural tests of the composite fuselage in Matsui study, were conducted applying the concept of “Building Block Approach” [3]. As the metallic fuselage can buckle with a small % of limit load, then the post buckling behaviour is very important to gain weigh saving when composite fuselage is designed to compare with metallic fuselage design. Many development were made to understand the post buckling behaviour [4], [5], [6], [7]. In the reference [5], observed the presence of post-buckling behavior as shown in Figure 3, and good numerical correlation versus experimental data, in special for initial buckling load for a given configuration of the specimen. In the reference [7] as can be seen in Fig. 4 - Future Design Scenario for Typical Stringer Stiffened Composite Panel, the initial buckling load (BL) will start well below the limit load (LL). Thus, there is a large level of post buckling behavior until the ultimate load (UL). Note that the ultimate load is very near the collapse load of the panel. Therefore,

this paper outlines the conception of the composite stiffened panel designed to shear and bending loading under post buckling behaviour [8] addressing the future design scenario as mentioned in the Fig. 4. This development was preceded by composite post buckling behaviour study of the closed box under bending and torsion loading [9], the crippling failure validation for two boundary conditions of the stiffener [10] and by composite stiffened box using bonded stiffeners [11]. In the reference [9], as shown in Figure 5, has highlighted the post-buckling behavior and the results were promising within the scope proposed.

In the present study, panels with stiffeners and frames using bonded process were used. In this investigation the stiffener and frames are disconnected. The theoretical analysis agreed very well with test results, showing the large capability of post buckling behaviour.

Fig. 1 - Stringers and Frame Cross-Section [2]

Fig. 2 - Shear Buckling Test of Stiffened Panel [2]

Fig. 3 - Typical Panel in Compression

Fig. 4 - Future Design Scenario for Typical Stringer Stiffened Composite Panel [7]

Fig. 5 - Typical Box in Bending and Twisting under Post Buckling Behaviour

2 Panel Definition

2.1 Conception, Geometry, Material and Manufacture

The composite stiffened panel is composed by two "Z" frames and four blade stiffeners. No connection exist between the frames and stiffeners. There are holes in the frames without restrictions to the stiffeners. Different configurations of the joint between the skin and the stiffener have been tested. The frames are bonded in the skin. The thickness in the skin permits the buckling between the stiffeners but avoids the rupture in the end of the test fixture. The material used is carbon/epoxy and the manufacture process is hand lay-up. The principal dimensions are showed in the Fig. 6 Panel General Dimensions. Fig. 7 shows the panel elements.

Fig. 6 - Panel General Dimensions [mm]

Fig. 7 - Panel Elements

2 Test Set-up: Loading and boundary condition

The test fixture was designed to permit a complete control during the test regarding the boundary conditions. One edge is clamped, on the other hand the opposite side is aligned with a linear guide, as showed in the Fig. 8 Loading and Boundary Conditions. Strain gages and LVDT (Linear Variable Differential Transformer) were used to verify the strains and displacements as showed in the Figure 9.

Fig. 8 - Loading and Boundary Conditions.

Fig. 9 - Strain Gages and LVDTs Configurations.

3 Test and Theoretical Results

As described in the previous topics the test setup was manufacture with careful, to keep the complete control about the boundary condition. As observed in the Figure 10, the function of the loaded tab is to assure that the rotation is equal zero. Also, in the attachment area where are the loading and clamped boundary condition, were reinforced to avoid failure in this region. The loading was applied until the complete failure of the panel.

For numerical simulation results was used finite element method with commercial software NASTRAN. Figure 11 shows the model used for structural analysis. Finite element plate (CQUAD4) with laminate properties (PComP) were used. In the skin/stiffener and skin/frame interfaces were used rigid elements to simulate the bonded interface. In more accurate analysis the cohesive elements were used. It is emphasized that the analysis concerned, several simplifying assumptions were adopted, so contact between the parts, curing residual stresses and friction on the rail loading were not considered. Figure 12 shows the result of elastic buckling simulation in the linear NASTRAN through the

solution 105. The figure shows the first buckling mode, relative to a vertical load applied. In the other hand, using a non-linear elastic analysis by including the effects of large displacements by NASTRAN solution 106, the Figure 13, shows the deformed post-buckling load failure on the first layer of the panel laminate (FPF: "first ply failure" using Tsai-Wu criteria). Although not shown in the Fig. 13, the initial buckling load by solution 106 is similar to the solution 105 of the Nastran.

The results of the numerical simulation for failure criteria of the skin is shown in Figure 14. The shaded areas in this figure represent the regions where started the failures. Two criteria were used in this simulation, the maximum strain and Tsai-Wu. Both showed similar results. The results for the frames is shown in Figure 15. It is observed that the critical regions are near the "mouse hole", but it does not have failures. The stiffeners also showed no failures.

Specimens were manufactured for the static test until ultimate failure. Also specimens were manufactured to be subjected to cyclic loading with subsequent static loading to verify residual strength. It was observed that the theoretical stiffness is very similar to panel stiffness until the initial buckling load. In the region after buckling, the theoretical stiffness is greater than the panel stiffness, as seen in other studies in the literature. It happens because it is not being considered the variability of the elastic properties of the panel after buckling. The failure load obtained by the numerical simulation was conservative with respect to the experimental result. The failure occurred in the tests is illustrated in Figure 16. In general, the failure started at opposite corners of the skin shown in the figure, and then propagated along the panel height, as a tearing. This led to localized failures in the frames mouse hole and also its detachment with skin. There was no disbond of the stiffeners in any of the cases tested.

Also a nonlinear analysis was performed using ABAQUS commercial software. The main purpose of this analysis was to study the progressive failure using cohesive elements. In this case, cohesive elements were used in all the interfaces between the frames and skin and also between stiffeners and skin. Figure 17 shows the panel model used in ABAQUS software. The results of simulation can be observed in

load-displacement curve showed in Figure 18. The curve shows that the first ply failure (FPF) occurs in the same load level obtained by NASTRAN software simulation. However, the difference between the ultimate load obtained by ABAQUS software and the maximum load supported by the panel was only 1.6%. That is, a good agreement with test results. In Figure 19 is shown the displacement at a time close to occurrence of the failure. The first elements that had total degradation in the finite element model are in the region that started the failure in experimental test.

The test results and the theoretical prediction agreed very well as showed in one strain gage of the Fig. 20. In this figure, continuous line is the test results. Initial imperfections, stiffness reduction after buckling, first and last failure criteria by Tsai-Wu [11] and interface analysis between stiffener and skin using cohesive element were also made [12].

Fig. 10 - Strain Gages and LVDTs Configurations

Fig. 11 - Finite Element Model (Nastran).

Fig. 12 - Buckling - Linear (Nastran)

Fig. 13 - Post-Buckling - Non Linear (Nastran).

Fig. 14 - Skin Critical Regions

Fig. 15 - Frames Critical Regions

Fig. 16 Failure Regions in the Test.

Fig. 20 Theoretical (-Δ-) versus Experimental (--).

Fig. 17 Abaqus Finite Element Model.

Fig. 18 Abaqus Finite Element Results.

Fig. 19 Abaqus Progressive Failure.

4 Conclusions

The weight can be the objective function in an optimum design. As the metallic fuselage can buckle with a loading below limit load, the composite fuselage should buckle below ultimate load, to be competitive in terms of weight. In the impossibility to have post buckling, a new design conception, can be a way to obtain the goal to weigh reduction. The literature has shown that a great capacity of post buckling behaviour is possible after buckling. To comply with this observation many development tests are necessary to obtain confidence. The results obtained with this present work using this conception, showed a great chance to have success in a design of composite fuselage.

References

- [1] D.R. Polland et al. "Global Cost and Weight Evaluation of Fuselage Side Panel Design Concepts", *NASA Contractor Report 4730*, LRC, April 1997.
- [2] N. Matsui and K. Sato, "Research Work of the All-Composite Fuselage Structure", *Proceedings of 14th International Conference on Composite Materials - ICCM14*, Vol. 1, ID 0900, pp 270, July 2003.
- [3] Composite Materials Handbook, "Volume 3 - Polymer Matrix Composites Materials Usage, Design, and Analysis", *MIL-HDBK-17-3F*, June 2002.
- [4] R. Zimmermann, "POSICOSS - Improved Postbuckling Simulation for Design of Fibre Composite Stiffened Fuselage Structures", *Composite Structures*, Volume 73, Issue 2, pp 171-174, May 2006.
- [5] C. Bisagni, H. Abramovich, T. Weller, "Buckling Behavior of Composite Laminated Stiffened Panels under Combined Shear and Axial Compression", *46th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural*

Dynamics & Materials Conference, pp 18-21 April 2005.

- [6] G. Romeo, G. Frulla, "Post-buckling Behaviour of Graphite/epoxy Stiffened Panels with Initial Imperfections Subjected to Eccentric Biaxial Compression Loading", *Int J Non-Linear Mech* 32(6): pp 1017–33, 1997.
- [7] R. Degenhardt, R. Rolfes, R. Zimmermann, K. Rohwer, "COCOMAT - improved material exploitation of composite airframe structures by accurate simulation of postbuckling and collapse", *Composite Structures* 73, 175-178, 2006.
- [8] A. Gavazzi and F.K. Arakaki, "Composite Stiffened Panel Post Buckling Test Proposal", *EMRAER Technical Report DTICSZ013 Rev -*, November 2007.
- [9] F.K. Arakaki and J.C.D. Santos, "Composite Box Test Proposal", *EMBRAER Technical Report 500SRZ001 Rev -*, October 2005.
- [10] A. Gavazzi and F.K. Arakaki, "Composite Crippling Test Proposal", *EMBRAER Technical Report DTICSZ002 Rev-*, August 2006.
- [11] F.K. Arakaki and P.R. Pasquali, "Composite Stiffened Box Test Proposal", *EMBRAER Technical Report DTICSZ044 Rev-*, June 2008.
- [12] S.W. Tsai, "Strength and Life of Composites", *Stanford: Composites Design Group, Department of Aeronautics & Astronautics, Stanford University*, 1st ed , 2008.
- [13] C.G. Dávila, P.P. Camanho, A. Turon, "Cohesive Elements for Shells", *NASA/TP-2007-214869*, April 2007.